

Resilience, Sustainability, and Social Justice Panel

Resource Document

Moderator: [Julie Ivy](#), Professor, College of Engineering

Panelists

- [Angela Harris](#), Assistant Professor, College of Engineering
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Zakiya Leggett](#), Assistant Professor, College of Natural Resources
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Jennifer Runkle](#), Research Scholar, North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
 - [Mary Watzin](#), Professor, College of Natural Resources
 - [Watch Opening Remarks](#)
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Event Description:

The adverse impacts of climate change tend to disproportionately affect BIPOC communities, lower-income areas and other historically underprivileged socioeconomic groups. Bringing together experts in coastal resilience and sustainability, environmental epidemiology, forest and soil ecology, and water treatment infrastructure, this panel explores the intersection of climate and human health in the context of resilience sustainability and societal inequality — and highlights ways NC State strives to ensure that those who are most at risk don't get overlooked.

You can [watch](#) the discussion in its entirety on the NC State Research YouTube channel.

Online Resources Shared:

- Article - Without inclusion, diversity initiatives may not be enough:
<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/357/6356/1101>
 - Coastal Resilience and Sustainability Initiative White Paper:
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/198DncT0vwOGKEx7kp7yKfbnASBpo4f7k/view?usp=sharing>
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The following questions were answered live during the 2021 University Research Symposium Resilience, Sustainability and Social Justice Panel. Under each question we provide links you can use to jump directly to the point in the video recording where the question was asked.

Which climate related issue(s) is your research most focused on currently?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)

How can the research community work to ensure local and regional resilience?

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Zakiya, can you tell us a little bit more about your work with BIPOC students and their interest in applied ecology work? Does this relate back to their needs in their community?

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Do you feel that BIPOC communities are equally/unequally affected by routine hurricanes and tornadoes as well as novel pandemic or layered events, emergencies or crisis? What are some of the areas that we can work on to better respond within these communities to build resilience?

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Angela, how have you or could you include agriculture in your work, especially those involved in animal agriculture in eastern North Carolina?

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Do our NC State extension offices have the climate resilience training and data they need to communicate risks and adaptation measures for stakeholders?

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When we discuss the development of local solutions should we be engaging stakeholders who are upstream and maybe creating or amplifying problems in another community?

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How do you engage across stakeholder groups and what are the best methods available to us, based on your experience?

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Is there potential to utilize engineers without borders, extensive experience and strategic approach methods for engaging local communities?

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What does our next generation of extension specialists look like? How should they be trained, if we want to augment our current status? From your perspective, what do you think NC State needs to do at an institutional level to support scientists in order to do better community and stakeholder engagement?

[Watch the Full Answer](#)